

Assessment of Human Resource Capacity of Construction Companies in Nepal

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Abstract

People management is one of the most essential Resources. The research work intended to assess the capacity of people of class A contractors in Nepal. Among the A Class contractors having their office at Kathmandu, 30 contractors were randomly selected for survey and schedule of the action research. Descriptive and use of statistical tools like percentage mean calculation method (Direct Method) along with Comparative study Study of Present HR capacity of Nepalese Construction firms & HR requirement for ICB contract were done.

Line Organization Structure was found to be adopted with three departments. Existing Class A Construction Companies are much more capable in terms of HR (Numbers, Experience & Projects Handled). Most of the companies follow management determination with best match for promotion decision rules whereas very few companies give promotion to their employees only on the basis of seniority. Regarding Health & Safety performance, the company follows a lot regarding safety rules, use of safety equipment, documentation & hazard analysis where as the company provides only a few health & safety training to a limited person which is required by laws. The health & safety policies are generally generated by managers only & for the very few times only employees are involved in developing the policies jointly. Health & safety policies, guidelines must be developed with the full assistance of employees working at site & the management team. Company must provide facilities like incentive package, well fare facilities to all their employees to hold them in the company for long time.

Keywords: Acquire, Development, Motivate, Maintenance, Utilization, International Competitive Bidding (ICB) Contracts

Introduction

Hydropower projects Performance of Construction industry in Nepal is not found very impressive (Chilawal and Mishra, 2018). Even Town Development Projects are found to be far behind in Time performance (Mishra and Bhandari, 2018). Relation of performance and productivity has been established by Chilawal and Mishra (2017) in Hydropower projects of Nepal. Several factors have been identified by Chilawal and Mishra(2018). Even causes of disputes were found as human performance in Asian Development Bank funded road projects (Mishra et. al., 2018). Human resource development & effective management is one of the important parameters which are required to be implemented. Without correct use of Human Resource &

effective implementation of its management one cannot imagine the success of any industry. That is why we say human resources are the backbone of construction industry & especially for the cases of labor based technology. Also due to lack of job opportunities in Nepal most of the people go abroad for jobs & higher studies & settle there. So every year youth forces are decreasing which may directly or indirectly hamper the construction industry. Human resource being importance for construction industry, the study of Human Resources & its management in construction industry is not yet done. So for the success & strengthen of the human resource capacity for construction industry, the study of Human resource capacity & its management is required.

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Also for infrastructure development projects or mega projects to carry out in Nepal most of the funding agencies like ADB, WB, JICA, etc request to select the contractor by ICB method & give less priority to NCB method as Nepalese contractors lack experiences, financial soundness, equipment holding, human resources & management skills. This makes the foreign contractor in to the country either in the form of main contractor or sometimes in the form of petty contractor which is the danger sign of pushing out Nepalese contractor out of the business. Also from government side no systematic effort has been made to develop human resource for construction industry.

So the contractors to remain in the market & compete & participate in NCB as well as ICB contracts they need to boost up their capacity in terms of capital, technical, financial, equipment, human resources & management up to the international level. It is possible only when government support the contractors by giving subsidiary in the field of human resource development. Besides the study of all capacity my study regarding human resources capacity of contractors could help to analyze & give information about how HR are managed & whether the human resources are enough in the contractor to do & manage the mega projects. The general objective of the study is to access Human Resource capacity of A class contractors in Nepal.

Empirical Review

According to Adhikari, 2014, there are many rumors and conflicts about the capability of Nepalese contractors about their technical and financial ability for not completing the projects undertaken by them within the given timeframe and of standard quality. Although construction entrepreneur of Class A in Nepal, have the opportunities to withstand in construction industry (as country is still in construction phase of infrastructure development) with full enthusiasm and effort, they seems to be demoralized by the policies, rules, guidance and support from the government and procedure of procurement of donor agencies during bidding in Mega Projects. The objective of the research was to compare the existing equipment capabilities of Class A construction entrepreneurs with the prescribed requirement as per CBA 2055 & CBR 2056 and also to determine the current capacity of the class A construction entrepreneurs in terms of technical and financial capabilities. The researcher adopted close ended question, open ended question, and ranking method of prioritization was adopted to obtain the necessary data from the respondents. The respondents were selected randomly. Percentage, frequency and charts were used to analyze the data. The result has showed that, in owning equipments most of the companies have failed to meet the prescribed standard as per CBA 2055 & CBR 2056. Only few numbers of contractors are extremely satisfied with their business. The research has also shown the unavailability

of human resources in tunnel sector, hydropower sector and bridge sector in construction sector in present context.

For the betterment of the Construction Industries the researcher has recommended that the Contractors need to focus in some particular area or sector of construction work instead of targeting almost all the sectors in order to expertise in a particular sector to enhance the quality and specialization of work. There should be a systematic monitoring system for to maintain the standard of equipment of class A contractors after the issuance of license as class A. Special training for labors should be provided to produce the skilled manpower in tunnel sector, hydropower sector and bridge sector.

Furthermore, as per Adoko, (2010) on a study of Human Resource Management & performance in Uganda Construction Industry Human Resource Management (HRM) can be viewed as core processes of the construction companies, affecting the way the organization acquires and uses human resources, and how employees experience the employment relationship. Traditional sources of competitiveness in construction industry, such as production capacities, financial resources, raw materials, distribution channels, are considered necessary, but no longer sufficient for organizational success.

Human resources, their knowledge, skills and competencies as well as their synergy among them, become the most valuable asset, the new source of wealth, and the key ingredient of competitive advantage. Consequently, the human resources function, which deals with planning, development, and keeping the best people, now has the opportunity to move out of the background into the mainstream of organizational strategy and management.

Results indicate that the Uganda construction industry on average has insufficient HR activities. Precisely, Pearson chi square showed that training which the source of sustained competitive advantage was not common among the construction firms. Consequently, HRM in Uganda construction industry could not be considered a solid ground for achieving competitiveness through people.

Workforce Management and Performance

The study indicated by Bhatta et. al. (2018) that the civil engineers working in the building sector in construction firms in Nepal were generally satisfied with their job with average the job satisfaction score 3.54 though they were unsatisfied with the pay system and promotional opportunities. The contractors don't provide health facilities at the construction site for causal workers. They are compelled to work without proper sanitary facilities, safe drinking water, no proper catering service and others. Employees think that health related facilities are lacking in the site (Mishra and Sharestha, 2017). Korala(2012) also

highlighted these issues in Nepalese infrastructure project constructions. A good performance of any construction projects refers that it is free from defects, right things at right time and the continuous improvement of the project (Chilwal & Mishra, 2018). The study conducted by Maskey and Mishra (2018) showed that time spent by skilled and unskilled labors in productive work were 56.92% and 55.74% respectively. It means rest of their time still unused. So it needs to manage all level of workforce effectively for high performance of the industry. Mishra and Rai (2017) also compared the different types of building and found performance should improve for which People management is most.

Methodology

The researcher collected list of Class A contractors that are registered & associate members of FCAN with their name, contact address & telephone number from FCAN, Kathmandu office. Then, the list of 40 respondents (about 30% of population) was selected by random sampling method. The respondents were then at first contact in telephone providing information about the research criteria & hence distributed questionnaire by personal meetings. 15 respondents answered the questions with the direct interaction with the researcher whereas for 10 respondents hard copy was distributed & for 15 respondents questions were distributed by email. All the respondents i.e. 10 nos. of respondents returned hardcopy & 15 nos. of respondents who were mailed returned in email. The total time taken to

collect all the 40 respondents' data's was about 4 months. Summary is presented in table 1.

Results and Analysis

General Information

Experience on Specialized Construction of Work by Class A Construction Companies

Generally, there are many sectors in which any firm can take part in construction work of interested area after meeting specific criteria of qualification. But there has also been argue that there is a need of Building Contractor, Road Contractor, Pavement Contractor, Bridge Contractor, tunnel Contractor, Hydropower Contractor or similar specialist contractor so as to enhance at competitive cost also.

Table 2. Experience on Specialized Construction of Work by Class A Construction Entrepreneurs

S.No.	Response	Number	%
1.	Yes	13	32.5
2.	No	27	67.5
	Total	40	100

As shown in table2, 4.1, 32.5% of the firms are specialized in particular construction works whereas, remaining 67.50% of the firms are engaged in two or more than two areas of construction works like building , road, bridges, hydropower, etc on the basis of their capacity.

Table 1. Research Matrixes

S.No.	Objectives	Types of Data	Data Source	Analysis Method	Expected Outcomes
1.	To find out the HR capacity of A class contractors	Questionnaire Survey	Primary Construction companies	Descriptive and use of statistical tools like percentage, mean calculation method (Direct Method)	Identify the existing strength in terms of HR
2..	To analyze the HR management practices (Acquire, Development, Motivate, maintain & Use)	Questionnaire Survey	Primary Construction Firms	Descriptive and use of statistical tools like percentage, mean calculation method	Information about Present Scenario of HR practice
3.	To analyze the Capacity of Nepalese Contracting firm in terms of HR requirement for ICB contract	Primary Questionnaire Survey & Secondary Literature Review	Primary Construction Companies & Secondary Literature Review (Journals, Articles published by FCAN, ICB related Documents, ADB / WB / JICA published	Comparative study Study of Present HR capacity of Nepalese Construction firms & HR requirement for ICB contract	Know the competitive status of Nepalese Contracting Firms for ICB contract requirement

Figure 1. Work Experience Sector of Class A Construction Companies

As shown in Figure 1, 95% of the respondents are involved in Construction and maintenance of building, 77.5% of the respondents are involved in Road Construction and maintenance whereas only 27.5% of the respondents are involved in Tunnel, sub-way work. Similarly, 67.5% of the respondents are involved in both Airport Building and maintenance & Barrage, canal, reservoir, water tank & maintenance work. Also, from the above figure it is seen that equal respondents i.e. 35% are involved in both Hydraulic Structure work and Re-construction & maintenance of work.

Therefore, most of the contractors have experienced of construction of works in more than two different construction areas especially in Construction and maintenance of Building, Road Construction & Maintenance. The research also shows that very few contractors are involved in tunnel, sub way work & Hydraulic structure work.

HR Capacity

Human resource capacity is about ensuring that an organization has enough people with the necessary skills to achieve its objectives.

Types of Organization Structure followed by Class A Construction Companies

Organization Structure determines how the roles, power and responsibilities are assigned, controlled, and coordinated, and how information flows between the different levels of management.

A structure depends on the organization's objectives and strategy. In a centralized structure, the top layer of management has most of the decision making power and has tight control over departments and divisions. In a decentralized structure, the decision making power is distributed and the departments and divisions may have different degrees of independence.

Therefore, most of the companies follow Line Organization Structures & secondly staff or functional authority organization structure & project organization structure

Table 3. Types of Organization of Class A Construction Companies

S.No.	Organization Structure	No.	%
1	Line Organization Structure	18	45
2	Staff or Functional Authority Organization Structure	13	32.5
3	Line & Staff Organization Structure	1	2.5
4	Divisional Organization Structure	0	0
5	Project Organization Structure	13	32.5
6	Matrix Organization Structure	3	7.5
7	Hybrid Organization Structure	2	5

where as none of the organization follows Divisional Organizational Structure.

Existing Departments of Class A Construction Companies

Table 4. Different Departments possess by Class A Construction Companies

S.No.	Name of the Department	No.	%
1	Procurement Department	32	80
2	Marketing & Sales Department	13	32.5
3	Accounting & Finance Department	35	87.5
4	Human Resource Department	12	30
5	Information Technology Department	7	17.5
6	Technical Department	36	90
7	Legal & Claim Department	19	47.5
9	All of Above	8	20

This result reveals that most of the companies have minimum three departments i.e. Procurement department, Accounting & Finance Department & Technical Department whereas only few companies have additional departments like Human Resource Department & Legal & claim department.

Range of Human Resources available in each Department of Class A Construction Companies has been shown in table 5.

Technical Human Resources available in Class A Construction Companies

Human resources are the set of individuals who make up the workforce of an organization, business sector, or economy. Technical Human resources in construction sector generally refer to the various personal like engineers who can be in

Table 5. Range of HR available in each Department of Class A Construction Companies

S.No.	Name of the Department	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
1.	Procurement Department	0	32	8.9
2.	Marketing & Sales Department	0	32	5.0
3.	Accounting & Finance Department	0	35	13.3
4.	Human Resource Department	0	15	2.3
5.	Information Technology Department	0	16	1.7
6.	Technical Department	2	110	33.4
7.	Legal & Claim Department	0	10	2.0

the post of chairman. Managing Director, Technical Advisor, General Manager, Project Manager, Senior Engineer, Site Engineer, etc & then overseers, surveyors supervisors, etc. Range of Technical Human Resources available in Class A Construction Companies has been show in table 6.

Table 6. Range of Technical Human Resources in Class A Construction Companies

S.No.	Types of Manpower	Range of Technical Human Resources		
		Minimum	Maximum	Mean
1	Chairman	0	1	0.6
2	ED / MD	0	3	1.1
3	TA	0	5	1.2
4	GM	0	6	0.7
5	AGM	0	10	0.8
6	SPM	0	15	2.2
7	PM	0	16	5.7
8	SE	0	12	4.3
9	E	0	35	9.4
10	Intern	0	20	2.7
11	JE	0	32	8.0
12	Surveyors		40	5.9
13	Supervisors		120	17.5

MD=Managing Director, ED=Executive Director TA= Technical Advisor, GM=General Manager, AGM=Assistant General Manager, SPM=Senior Project Manager, PM=Project Manager, E=Engineer, JE=Junior Engineer

The mean value of each personnel was calculated by "Direct Mean Calculation Method".

MD=Managing Director, ED=Executive Director TA= Technical Advisor, GM=General Manager, AGM=Assistant

Table 7. Range of Non-Technical Human Resources in Class A Construction Companies

S.No.	Types of Human Resources	Range of Non-Technical Human Resources		
		Minimum	Maximum	Mean
1	Chairman	0	1	0.3
2	ED / MD	0	3	0.7
3	Advisor (Business/HR/PR)	0	2	0.5
4	GM	0	6	0.5
5	AGM	0	6	0.6
6	Manager (All Dept.)	0	8	2.4
7	Assistant Manager	0	16	2.5
8	Officer	0	18	5.2
9	Junior Officer	0	25	6.2
10	Office Secretary	0	30	2.5
11	Office Assistant	0	40	5.6
12	Heavy/light Driver	1	300	30.6

Range of Non-Technical Human Resources available in Class A Construction Companies

The mean value of each personnel was calculated by "Direct Mean Calculation Method".

Table 8. Average Human Resources in Class A Construction Companies

S.No.	Types of Human Resources	Avg. Human Resources
1	Technical Human Resources	59.4
2	Non-Technical Human Resources	57.6
	Total Avg. Human Resources	116.95

Work Experience of Technical Human Resources in Class A Construction Companies

The mean value of work experience of each personnel was calculated by "Direct Mean Calculation Method".

General Manager, SPM=Senior Project Manager, PM=Project Manager, E=Engineer, JE = Junior Engineer

Figure 2. Avg. Work Experience of Technical HR

The average work experience of each personnel was calculated by "Direct Mean Calculation Method".

MD=Managing Director, GM=General Manager, AGM=Assistant General Manager,

Figure 3. Avg. Work Experience of Non-Technical HR

No. of Projects that are successfully handled / completed by Technical Personnel of Class A Construction Companies

Table 9. No. of Projects that are Successfully Completed by Technical Personnel

S.No.	Types of MP	Range of Projects that are successfully completed		
		Minimum	Maximum	Mean
1	Chairman	6	16 & Above	15.52
2	ED / MD	10	16 & Above	15.06
3	Technical Advisor	8	16 & Above	14.10
4	GM	6	16 & Above	14.71
5	AGM	8	16 & Above	14.00
6	SPM	10	16 & Above	14.45
7	PM	6	16 & Above	12.06
8	SE	4	16 & Above	10.92

MD=Managing Director, ED=Executive Director TA= Technical Advisor, GM=General Manager, AGM=Assistant General Manager, SPM=Senior Project Manager, PM=Project Manager, SE=Senior Engineer

The mean value of successfully completed projects by different technical personnel was calculated by "Direct Mean Calculation Method" & presented in tabulated form.

No. of Projects that are successfully handled / completed by Non-Technical Personnel of Class A Construction Companies

Table 10. No. of Projects that are successfully handled by Non-Technical Personnel

S.No.	Types of MP	Range of Non-Technical Human Resources		
		Minimum	Maximum	Mean
1	Chairman	12	16 & Above	15.71
2	ED / MD	10	16 & Above	14.71
3	Advisor	6	16 & Above	12.67
4	General Manager	10	16 & Above	14.00
5	Asst. General Manager	10	16 & Above	14.15
6	Manager	4	16 & Above	11.17
7	Asst. Manager	4	16 & Above	9.76

MD=Managing Director, ED=Executive Director

Capacity of Technical Human Resources in terms of numbers, experiences & Projects that are successfully completed of Class A Construction Companies.

Table 11. Technical Human Resource Details Data

S.No.	Technical Human Resource Details Data			
	Post	Numbers	Work Experience	Project Handle
1.	Chairman	0.6	24.45	15.52
2.	ED / MD	1.1	21.63	15.06
3.	TA	1.2	19.13	14.10
4.	GM	0.7	17.74	14.71
5.	AGM	0.8	14.75	14.00
6.	SPM	2.2	17.95	14.45
7.	PM	5.7	14.89	12.06
8.	SE	4.3	11.74	10.92
9.	E	9.4	7.3	-
10.	Intern	2.7	1.71	-
11.	JE	8.0	9.61	-
12.	Surveyors	5.9	11.32	-
13.	Supervisors	17.5	12.31	-

Capacity of Non-Technical Human Resources in terms of numbers, experiences & Projects that are successfully completed of Class A Construction Companies

Under Construction Business Rules, 2056 (2000) Clause 10, Sub-rule 1, Schedule 10, numbers of key Human Resources required for Class A Construction Companies.

Table 12. Non-Technical Human Resource Details Data

S.No.	Non-Technical Human Resource Details Data			
	Post	Numbers	Work Experience	Project Handle
1.	Chairman	0.3	23.85	15.71
2.	ED / MD	0.7	20.58	14.71
3.	Advisor (Business/HR/PR)	0.5	17.71	12.67
4.	GM	0.5	17.15	14.00
5.	AGM	0.6	16.27	14.15
6.	Manager (All Dept.)	2.4	12.70	11.17
7.	Assistant Manager	2.5	9.69	9.76
8.	Officer	5.2	8.00	-
9.	Junior Officer	6.2	5.32	-
10.	Office Secretary	2.5	6.29	-
11.	Office Assistant	5.6	4.79	-
12.	Heavy/light Driver	30.6	10.69	-

But according to respondents as Nepal is a developing Country lots of budgets are allocated in Infrastructure development work every year due to which volume of works & challenges for contractors are increasing every year. So the allocated manpower as a norms in CBR, 2056(2000) is not enough & need revised accordingly.

HR System

Adaptation of computerized HR Information System by Class A Construction Companies was found to be practiced by 35 out of 40. Recruitment is an important part of the acquisition aspect of human resource management. It is the process of finding right people for right position at the right time. It is concerned with identifying & attracting a pool of qualified candidates to fulfill human resource needs of an organization. The quality of human resources very much depends on the quality of recruits. Recruitment should locate & attract a sufficiently large pool of qualified candidates for job vacancies. The process begins when new recruits are sought & ends when applications are received.

Most of the companies use Referrals from current staffs as recruitment sources & very few uses collage & equivalent program & employment agency as a recruitment sources.

Figure 4. Frequencies of Recruitment Sources used by Class A Construction Companies

Referrals from current staffs as a recruitment sources is much more effective sources comparison to others sources like employment agency, collage or equivalent program, on-line sources, advertisement.

Figure 5. Effectiveness of using recruitment sources in Class A Construction Companies

Allocation of an annual budget for every fiscal year for recruitment of Human resource of Class A Construction Companies were found in only 9 companies out of 40.

Selection

No Organization can function effectively without the right people. Selection is the process of choosing the most suitable candidates for a particular position from among the prospective applicants. The goal is to select the right person for the right job. Selection follows recruitment. It is concerned with hiring as well as rejecting the applicants.

The Company selects the best all around candidates when recruiting employees

The respondents agree or disagree towards the statement of selecting best all around candidates when recruiting employees.

40% of the respondents were strongly agreed towards the statement while only 2.5% of the respondents were strongly disagreed. 27.5% of the respondents were agreed to the statement whereas only 5% of the respondents were disagreed. 25% of the respondents were found neutral to the statement.

Therefore the chart reveals that most of the companies agreed with the statement whereas very few, in negligent amount, did not agree with the statement. Similarly, the respondents agree or disagree towards the statement of placing priority on a candidate's potential to learn when recruiting employees.

30% of the respondents were strongly agreed towards the statement while only 5% of the respondents were strongly disagreed. Most of the respondent's i.e.40% was agreed to the statement whereas only 7.5% of the respondents were disagreed. 17.5% of the respondents were found neutral to the statement.

Therefore, we can say that most of the companies (70%) agreed to the statement whereas very few (12.5%) only disagreed with the statement.

Even the respondents agree or disagree towards the statement of emphasizes traits and abilities required for providing high quality supports and services during Selection.

Most of the respondent's i.e.32.5% was strongly agreed towards the statement while only the least respondent's i.e. 5% were strongly disagreed. 30% of the respondents were agreed to the statement whereas only 7.5% of the respondents were disagreed. 25% of the respondents were found neutral to the statement.

From above analysis, we can say that most of the respondents (62.5%) give emphasizes on traits & abilities during selection while few are neutral to the statement & very few disagreed with the statement.

Figure 6. Responses to internal candidates of getting priority for job openings

Most of the respondents agreed of getting priority for job opening.

Most of the respondent's i.e.55 % was strongly agreed towards the statement while only 2.5% of the respondents were strongly disagreed & disagreed. 27.5% of the respondents were agreed to the statement. 12.5% of the respondents were found neutral to the statement.

The above analysis revealed that maximum no. of respondents agreed of getting opportunities for promotion if they are qualified.

Most of the respondent's i.e.45% was agreed towards the statement while only 5% of the respondents were strongly disagreed & disagreed. 22.5% of the respondents were strongly agreed & neutral to the statement.

Overall, most of the respondents agreed to the statement regarding discussion of values & beliefs in interviews with potential clients.

Promotion Decision Rules most often followed by Class A Construction Companies

Table 13. Promotion Decision Rules most often followed

S.No.	Statement	Response	Response in %
a.	merit or performance rating alone	13	32.5
b.	seniority only if merit is equal	4	10
c.	seniority among employees who meet a minimum merit requirement	9	22.5
d.	Seniority	1	2.5
e.	management determines best match with person supported	17	42.5

Most of the company's management decision is the final decision for promotion & it is good to see that very few companies give priority to solely on seniority for promotion.

Team Development & Training

Most of the respondents i.e. 45% agreed to the statement whereas only 2.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement of team's development as an important element. Similarly, 35% of the respondents said that they were strongly agreed with the statement & 17.5% of the respondents were neutral to the statement. So looking at the response from the respondents one can say that most of the companies agreed with the statement of development of team as an important element.

The Organization supports team development and training

Most of the respondents i.e. 47.5% agreed to the statement whereas only 7.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. Similarly, 20% of the respondents said that they were strongly agreed with the statement & 25% of the respondents were neutral to the statement. So we can say that most of the respondents agreed with the statement.

Most of the respondents i.e. 32.5% agreed to the statement whereas 20% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. Similarly, 22.5% of the respondents said that they were strongly agreed with the statement & 25% of the respondents were neutral to the statement.

The above data revealed that more than 50% of the respondents agreed to the statement whereas few respondents disagreed to the statement.

Most of the respondents i.e. 40% agreed to the statement whereas 25% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. Similarly, only 12.5% of the respondents said that they were strongly agreed with the statement & 22.5% of the respondents were neutral to the statement.

So we can say that only about 50% of the respondents agreed to the statement whereas few disagreed to it.

Training & Development

Training enhances capabilities required to improve performance in the present job. It involves positive changes in knowledge, skills & attitudes of employees to increase the efficiency & effectiveness on the job. Training serves as a balancing factor between employee capabilities & job requirements. It transforms the behavior of the individual.

Provision of Formal on Boarding Program for new Employees

It was found clear that 57.5% of the respondents said new employees are getting formal on boarding program whereas 42.5% of the respondents said new employees are not getting formal on boarding program.

No. of Days provided for Orientation program to new direct employees.

The mean value for orientation days provided by companies to their new employees are calculated by "Direct Mean value calculation Method" & presented the range of minimum, maximum & mean value.

No. of weeks required for a full time direct support employees to become fully competent on the job.

The mean value for no. of weeks required for full time direct support employees to become fully competent on the job are calculated by "Direct Mean value calculation Method" & presented the range of minimum, maximum & mean value. The average no. of weeks required for full time direct support employees to become fully competent on the job is 10.9.

Benefits Offered to Employees

57.5% of the respondents said only permanent staff are

getting medical insurance facility whereas 42.5% of the respondents said permanent staff are not getting medical insurance facility. Similarly, for temporary staff, only 42.5% of the respondents said they are getting medical insurance facility whereas 57.5% of the respondents said they are not getting medical insurance facility. For Contract basis staff, 37.5% of the respondents said contract basis staffs are getting medical insurance facility whereas 62.5% of the respondents said contract staffs are not getting medical facility.

47.5% of the respondents said permanent staffs are getting benefits of life insurance whereas 52.5% of the respondents said permanent staffs are not getting benefits of life insurance. Similarly, for temporary staff, only 12.5% of the respondents said they are getting life insurance facility whereas 87.5% of the respondents said they are not getting life insurance facility. For Contract basis staff, 32.5% of the respondents said contract basis staffs are getting life insurance whereas 67.5% of the respondents said contract basis staffs are not getting life insurance facility.

Only 40.0% of the respondents said permanent staffs are getting benefits of Employee Assistance Program whereas 60.0% of the respondents said permanent staffs are not getting benefits of Employee Assistance Program. Similarly, for temporary staff, very few i.e. 17.5% of the respondents said they are getting Employee Assistance Program facility whereas 82.5% of the respondents said they are not getting Employee Assistance Program facility. For Contract basis staff, 32.5% of the respondents said contract basis staffs are getting Employee Assistance Program whereas 67.5% of the respondents said contract basis staffs are not getting Employee Assistance Program facility.

Only 25.0% of the respondents said permanent staffs are getting benefits of Pension whereas 72.5% of the respondents said they are not getting benefits of Pension Plan. Similarly, for temporary staff, very few i.e. only 5.0% of the respondents said they are getting Pension facility whereas 95.0% of the respondents said they are not getting Pension facility. For Contract basis staff, they are not getting any Defined Pension Plan.

For Permanent Staff, Only 10.0% of the respondents said they are getting benefits of tuition Assistance program whereas 90.0% of the respondents said they are not getting benefits of Tuition Assistance Program.

Similarly, from above figure it is clear seen that as per the respondents (100% respondents) for temporary & Contract basis staff, they are not getting any benefits of tuition Assistance / Child Care Assistance facility.

From above figure, it is clear that very few (only 10%) permanent staffs get Tuition Assistance / Child Care Assistance facility except that none of the staffs get this facility at all from their companies.

47.5% of the respondents said permanent staffs are getting salary premium in lieu of benefits whereas 52.5% of the respondents said they are not getting any salary premium benefits.

Similarly, for temporary staff, very few i.e. only 15.0% of the respondents said they are getting salary premium facility whereas 85.0% of the respondents said they are not getting salary premium facility.

For Contract basis staff, 17.5% of the respondents said they are getting salary premium whereas 82.5% of the respondents said they are not getting any salary premium in lieu of benefits.

Performance Appraisal Method

A performance appraisal is a method by which the job performance of an employee is documented & evaluated. Performance appraisals are a part of career development & consist of regular reviews of employee performance within organizations.

Performance Appraisal Method used by Class A Construction Companies to measure the performance of employees

Table 14. Performance Appraisal Method used by Class A Construction Companies

S. No.	Performance Appraisal Method	Response	Response %
1.	Job Standard	26	65
2.	Comparison Oriented	6	15
3.	Objective Oriented	8	20
	Total	40	100%

It is seen that most of the companies use job standard as a performance Appraisal Method to measure the performance of employees.

Health & Safety Performance

Most of the respondents i.e. 42.5% agreed a lot that their companies has a formal system of tracking health & Safety performance indicators whereas only 15% of the respondents said their companies did not had formal system of tracking health & safety performance.

Similarly, 27.5% have moderate system for tracking health & safety performance whereas 15% have a little formal system for tracking health & safety performance indicators.

30.0% of the respondents moderately agreed about a provision of health & safety training that is required by law whereas 15% of the respondents said their companies did not provide any health & safety training.

Similarly, 27.5% have a lot believe that their companies

provide health & safety training that is required by law & again 27.5% have a little believe that their companies provide health & safety training that is required by law.

27.5% of the respondents agreed a lot about a provision of health & safety policies that is developed jointly between managers & employees whereas 17.5% of the respondents said their companies did not involve employees to make health & safety policies.

Similarly, 32.5% have a little agreed that their companies' involved employees to make health & safety policies & 22.5% have moderately agreed that their companies involved employees to make health & safety policies.

Facility/ Support to Maintain / Hold Company's Employees

45% of the respondents agreed a lot towards the statement of getting salary as per their job description whereas 5% of the respondents did not agreed at all with the statement.

Similarly, 37.5% of the respondents agreed moderately to the statement whereas 12.5% of the respondents agreed a little to the statement.

Only 17.5% of the respondents agreed a lot towards the statement of providing incentive as a facility to hold their employees whereas 15% of the respondents did not agreed at all with the statement.

Similarly, 35.0% of the respondents agreed moderately to the statement whereas 32.5% of the respondents agreed a little to the statement.

Most of the respondents i.e.55% agreed a lot towards the statement whereas only 2.5% of the respondents did not agree at all with the statement.

Similarly, 32.5% of the respondents agreed moderately to the statement whereas 10.0% of the respondents agreed a little to the statement.

20% of the respondents agreed a lot towards the statement that company address well to eradicate the case of grievance by employees whereas only 10% of the respondents did not agree at all with the statement.

Similarly, 45.0% of the respondents agreed moderately that company address well to eradicate the case of grievance by employees whereas 25% of the respondents agreed a little to the statement.

Only 32.5% of the respondents agreed a lot towards the statement of getting facility as a well fare from the companies whereas 7.5% of the respondents did not agreed at all with the statement. Similarly, 50% of the respondents agreed moderately to the statement whereas only 10% of the respondents agreed a little to the statement.

Conclusion

Instead of developing contractors themselves as a specialized contractors, most of the contractors are working in different fields of construction of works such as construction of buildings work, roads construction, etc. Line Organization Structure having minimum three departments i.e. Procurement Department, Accounting & Finance Department & Technical Department were found to be followed. Other important departments like Human Resource Department (30%) & legal & Claim Department (47.5%) exist only in some of the companies. Manpower allocation for Procurement department, Accounting & finance department & technical department is distinct comparison to other departments like Human resource department, marketing & sales department, Information Technology department & legal & Claim department. Average number of technical personnel is more comparison to non-technical personnel in the construction companies. According to the norms of Human Resource requirement for Class A Construction companies in Construction Business Rules, 2056 (2000) Clause 10, Sub-rule 1, and Schedule 10, existing Class A Construction Companies are much more capable in terms of HR (numbers, experience & projects handled) Most of the companies (87.5%) do not have any computerized HR information system. Referrals from current staff is the frequently used (62.5%) recruitment sources used by different companies as it is much more effective (70%) process compare to other recruitment sources. Most of the companies (77.5%) never plan any budget in any fiscal years for recruitment of Human Resources. According to the respondents recruitment of Human Resources solely depends upon the no. of new projects own by bidding of contract during that year. Most of the respondents are satisfied with selection procedure of the company especially getting of opportunity for promotion to new employees. Most of the companies follow management determination with best match for promotion decision rules whereas very few companies give promotion to their employees only on the basis of seniority. More than 50% of the companies provide formal on boarding program to new employees. On average 3.1 days are provided for orientation program to new direct employees & it takes on average 10.9 weeks for full time direct support employees to become fully competent on the job. Permanent staffs are getting more benefits like medical insurance, life insurance, Employee Assistance Program, Pension Plan, Tuition Assistance, Salary Premium in lieu of benefits compare to temporary staffs & very few to contract basis staffs. Job Standard Method is mostly used as Performance appraisal method by most of the companies to measure the performance of employees compare to other methods like comparison method & objective oriented method. Regarding Health & Safety performance, the company follows a lot regarding safety rules, use of safety equipment, documentation & hazard analysis whereas the company provides only a

few health & safety training to a limited person which is required by laws. The health & safety policies are generally generated by managers only & for the very few times only employees are involved in developing the policies jointly. Most of the employees of the companies agreed a lot that they are paid as per their job description. However, Incentive schemes are designed only to limited companies. Most of the employees of the companies follow rules & regulations & acceptable behavior of the company. But the companies put effort partially only to eradicate the cases of grievance by employees. Also the companies provide limited facilities like Safety/health/social security/sports/recreation/canteen, etc (one or two among them) according to the project types / volume / location.

Recommendations

In this 21st Century, it is seen from the study that most of the company do not follow any computerized HR information System. To smooth the function & management of HR, it is recommended to use latest & advance software for HR information system.

Meeting the criteria of Qualification, work experience, seniority & then management decision must be the basic rules for promotion in the company.

Training related to job must be given timely as a refreshment & motivational package.

All kinds of benefits like medical insurance, life insurance, Employee Assistance Program, Pension, Tuition fee, Salary premium in lieu of benefits, etc must be provided not only to permanent staff but also to temporary & contract basis staffs to hold/ retain in the company for long time & decrease turnover rate.

Regular health & safety training (follow safety rules, use of safety equipment, documentation, health hazard, hazard analysis, etc) must be provided to all kinds of employees working at site. Health & safety policies, guidelines must be developed with the full assistance of employees working at site & the management team. Further study based on specific sector should be conducted.

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